

COMPOSITION OF URANYL FERRO AND FERRICYANIDES BY PHYSICO-CHEMICAL METHODS. PART I. CONDUCTOMETRIC STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF URANYL FERROCYANIDE

BY JAGDISH N. GAUR, H. C. GAUR AND ABANI K. BHATTACHARYA

The composition of uranyl ferrocyanide has been studied by conductometric titrations of uranyl nitrate and potassium ferrocyanide at several concentrations in aqueous and aqueous alcoholic solutions. The compositions obtained both by direct and reverse titrations are analogous, and the equivalence points both in the direct and reverse titrations indicate the formation of the compound $K_2(UO_2)Fe(CN)_6 \cdot xUO_2(NO_3)_2$ which, in all probability, are adsorption complexes.

There is hardly any reference in the literature on the study of the uranyl ferrocyanide by physico-chemical methods. Atanasiu (*Bul. Soc. romana, Stiinta*, 1928, 30, 69) investigated the composition of uranyl ferrocyanide by potentiometry, but his conclusions were undecisive. Due to high adsorptive property of uranyl ferrocyanide, and also due to its hydrolysable character, analytical methods have not so far afforded any conclusive results.

Physico-chemical methods have, by far, given more conclusive evidences for the composition of many insoluble ferro- and ferricyanides (Bhattacharya and Gaur, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 487, 499; 1948, 25, 27, et seq.). In this paper the results obtained by conductometric titrations are communicated and the nature of the composition of uranium ferrocyanide obtained from the equivalence points has been discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Analar (B.D.H.) reagents were used. Preparation of standard solutions and further dilutions were done with conductivity water. Potassium ferrocyanide solution was estimated as described in a previous publication (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 473). Uranium in uranyl nitrate solution was estimated as U_3O_8 by evaporating 25 c.c. of the prepared (A/2) solution, in a platinum crucible, on a water-bath and heating the residue in full flame of a Mecker burner until the weight of the precipitate was constant. The measurements of conductance were done by Kohlrausch's universal Bridge (W. G. Pye). As a source of A. C., a low frequency oscillator (1000 c/s. Philips type 4260/1, No. RT-267) was used, the point of balance being indicated by a minimum of sound in the headphone. The conductivity cell was of Arrhenius type and during the course of titration it was kept immersed in a thermostat maintained at room temperature (31°). The titrations were carried out by taking 10 c.c. of one of the reactants in the conductivity cell while the other was added gradually from the burette. The conductance of the solution after each addition was measured and was corrected for dilution effect by multiplying the observed conductance by $v/10$, where v was the total volume of the solution and 10 c.c. referred to the volume of the reactant taken in the cell (Davies, "The Conductivity of Solutions", p. 238). Curves were plotted between the corrected

TABLE I

Direct titrations.

Theoretical value : 10 c.c. of $M/4.855 K_4FeCy_6 \equiv 10.117$ c.c. of $M/4.912 UO_2(NO_3)_2$.

A/10- K_4FeCy_6 in the cell (v c.c.)	Alcohol added.	$UO_2(NO_3)_2$ required for v c.c. of A/10 $K_4FeCy_6(v_1)$.	$UO_2(NO_3)_2$ calc. for 10 c.c. of A/10- K_4FeCy_6 [(v ₁ /v) 10].	Equiv. vol. of A/10- $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ [$\pi(v_1/v) 10$].	Compound formed.	Curve
A/1- $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ added to A/10- K_4FeCy_6 . Conc. ratio (π) = 10 : 1.						
10 c.c.	0 c.c.	1.16	1.16	11.6	$K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6$ 0.146 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$	1
9	1	1.00	1.11	11.1	$K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6$ 0.097 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$	2
8	2	0.88	1.10	11.0	$K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6$ 0.087 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$	3
A/2- $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ added to A/10- K_4FeCy_6 . Conc. ratio (π) = 5 : 1.						
10 c.c.	0 c.c.	2.3	2.3	11.5	$K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6$ 0.136 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$	4
9	1	2.0	2.22	11.1	$K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6$ 0.097 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$	5
8	2	1.76	2.20	11.0	$K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6$ 0.087 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$	6

TABLE II

Reverse titrations.

Theoretical value : 9.88 c.c. of $M/4.855 K_4FeCy_6 \equiv 10$ c.c. of $M/4.912 UO_2(NO_3)_2$.

A/10- $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ in the cell (v c.c.)	Alcohol added.	K_4FeCy_6 reqd. for v c.c. of $UO_2(NO_3)_2 (v_1)$.	K_4FeCy_6 calc. for 10 c.c. of $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ [10 (v ₁ /v)].	Equiv. vol of A/10- K_4FeCy_6 [$\pi (v_1/v) 10$].	Compound formed.	Curve.
A/1- K_4FeCy_6 added to A/10- $UO_2(NO_3)_2$. Conc. ratio (π) = 10 : 1.						
10 c.c.	0 c.c.	0.83	0.83	8.3	$K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6$ 0.190 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$	
9	1	0.76	0.84	8.4	$K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6$ 0.176 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$	
8	2	0.68	0.85	8.5	$K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6$ 0.162 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$	
A/2- K_4FeCy_6 added to A/10- $UO_2(NO_3)_2$. Conc. ratio (π) = 5 : 1.						
10 c.c.	0 c.c.	1.68	1.68	8.4	$K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6$ 0.176 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$	
9	1	1.56	1.73	8.65	$K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6$ 0.142 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$	
8	2	1.40	1.75	8.75	$K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6$ 0.129 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$	6

conductance thus obtained against the volume of the reactant. The breaks in the curves correspond to the formation of the different complexes. Using different concentrations of the two salt solutions, titrations were performed by direct and reverse methods, *i.e.* when uranyl nitrate from the burette was added to potassium ferrocyanide in the cell and *vice versa*. Titrations were done in the presence of alcohol up to 20% by volume. A/1 potassium ferrocyanide solution corresponds to $M/4.855$ and A/1 uranyl nitrate solution corresponds to $M/4.912$.

The results of the conductometric titrations have been summarised in Tables I and II.

D I S C U S S I O N .

From column five in the above tables it will be seen that in direct titrations the volume of uranyl nitrate required for 10 c.c. of potassium ferrocyanide is slightly more than that required for the formation of the compound in the molar ratio of 1:1. The discrepancy between the calculated and observed titre values gradually reduces by increasing the amount of alcohol in aqueous alcoholic solutions. The molecular composition of uranyl ferrocyanide obtained from the equivalence points both in the direct and reverse titrations corresponds to the compound $K_2UO_2FeCy_6 \cdot x UO_2(NO_3)_2$, where x varies slightly with the concentration ratio of the reactants. The value of x also varies with the quantity of alcohol added to the solution taken in the beaker. These observations suggest that the higher value of uranyl nitrate than the calculated one in direct titration, and lower value of potassium ferrocyanide in the reverse titrations result from the selective adsorption of uranyl nitrate by the precipitate of uranyl ferrocyanide.

In the direct titration the reaction takes place in the medium of potassium ferrocyanide, and hence, an adsorption compound with potassium ferrocyanide can be anticipated, but the result of the titration shows that the precipitated complex takes more uranyl nitrate at the equivalence point which results in the formation of an adsorption compound with uranyl nitrate. This seems to be due to much greater adsorption of uranyl nitrate than potassium ferrocyanide by the precipitated complex. The hydrolysis of uranyl ferrocyanide may also be responsible for a similar result according to the equation

The hydrolysed product $K_2H_2FeCy_6$ may now combine with more of uranyl nitrate than the equivalent amount resulting in the formation of a complex of the type $K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6 \cdot xUO_2(NO_3)_2$, the value of x depending upon the degree of hydrolysis of the precipitated complex.

In the reverse titration also the formation of an analogous compound can be explained. In this case a greater adsorption of uranyl nitrate can be anticipated since the reaction takes place in the medium of uranyl nitrate. The hydrolysis of $K_2UO_2FeCy_6$ can also bring about the formation of similar complexes, because uranyl nitrate will be partly used up by the hydrolysed product $K_2H_2FeCy_6$ during the course of the reaction, and hence, the titre value of potassium ferrocyanide at the equivalent point will be much less than the theoretical amount.

FIG. 1 (curve 1)

FIG. 2 (curves 2 and 3)

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

FIG. 5.

Reverse Titrations

FIG. 8

FIG. 7

FIG. 6

It is difficult to allocate the proportional contribution of adsorption and hydrolysis towards the formation of such compounds as have been observed, viz., $K_2UO_2FeCy_6$, $xUO_2(NO_3)_2$. Experimental work on the hydrolysis and adsorption of uranyl ferrocyanide is in progress and the results will form a later communication.

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COMPOSITION OF URANYL FERRO AND FERRICYANIDES BY PHYSICO-CHEMICAL METHODS. PART II. POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF URANYL FERROCYANIDE

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The composition of uranyl ferrocyanide has been studied by potentiometric titration of uranyl nitrate and potassium ferrocyanide at several concentrations in aqueous and aq. alcoholic solutions. The composition of uranyl ferrocyanide indicated by the equivalence points corresponds to the type $K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6$, $xUO_2(NO_3)_2$. There is a good agreement between the observations by potentiometry and conductometry.

In continuation of our observations on conductometric titrations between uranyl nitrate and potassium ferrocyanide (this issue, p. 158) potentiometric titrations were carried out between the same reactants. Atanasiu (*Bull. Soc. romana, Stiinta*, 1928, 30, 69) investigated the composition of uranyl ferrocyanide by potentiometry but his conclusions were undecisive. Our observation on the composition of uranyl ferrocyanide by potentiometry is in agreement with those obtained by conductometric titrations and the results have been discussed in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Analar (B.D.H.) reagents were used. Uranium in the solution of uranyl nitrate was estimated as U_3O_8 as described in part I (*loc. cit.*). The solution of potassium ferrocyanide was estimated by titrating against a standard solution of potassium permanganate.

In all the titrations potassium ferrocyanide containing 1% potassium ferricyanide was used (Kolthoff, Kolthoff and Furman, "Potentiometric Titrations"). Platinum was used as an indifferent electrode (Muller, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1914, 88, 44) which was used in conjunction with the saturated calomel electrode.

Ferri-ferrocyanide solution was dropped gradually from the burette into the solution of uranyl nitrate and the fall in E.M.F. was measured after each addition. Graphs were plotted between $E(\text{obs.})$ against the volume of ferrocyanide added. The equivalence point was found out from the steep fall in the potential indicated by the titration curves.